

SHORT NOTES

EFFECT OF AZOTOBACTER ON FIXED NITROGEN

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The utilisation of fixed nitrogen by *azotobacter vinelandii* has been investigated by using colorimetric and growth methods. It has been found that butylamine and semicarbazide, which are reduceable to ammonia, are utilised while nitrobenzene, benzyl nitrite and benzyl nitrate, which are not reduceable to ammonia, are not utilised by the bacteria. The lag period in case of compounds utilised increases with increase of concentration. It has been shown in the previous paper (Azim and Saraf, *Biochim. biophys. Acta*, 1956, 21, 321) that those nitrogenous compounds are utilised by *azotobacter vinelandii* which are likely to be reduced to ammonia. To confirm this further, the utilisation of butylamine, benzylamine, benzyl nitrite and benzyl nitrate, semicarbazide, nitrobenzene and pyridine has been investigated.

Procedure.—The flasks containing identical quantity of sterile medium inoculated with a culture containing 10^9 cells per 25 c.c. were kept at 30° and made 10^{-3} , 10^{-3} or 10^{-4} M with respect to the substrate by the addition of a suitable volume of the concentrated substrate solution. A known volume of the test solution was withdrawn at intervals and analysed by the usual colorimetric methods.

Butylamine.—Two concentrations of butylamine were studied (10^{-2} and 10^{-3} M). The concentration of the amine was determined colorimetrically in samples withdrawn at intervals with sodium nitroprusside in acetone. The method gave satisfactory results only with higher concentrations of the substrate. It was found that butylamine was utilised after a certain lag period (Table I).

Semicarbazide.—In this case the colorimetric method could not be used due to non-availability of the reagents. Therefore, the growth method (*J. Bact.*, 1950, 60, 369) was adopted. It was found that semicarbazide was utilised after a certain lag period in concentrations ranging from 10^{-2} to 10^{-6} M.

Benzylamine.—Benzylamine was studied in concentration ranging from 10^{-1} to 10^{-3} M. It was estimated colorimetrically at intervals using sodium nitroprusside in the presence of acetone. It was not utilised by the bacteria in spite of its non-toxic nature.

Benzyl nitrite and benzyl nitrate were studied in concentrations ranging from 10^{-3} to 10^{-4} M and estimated colorimetrically—nitrates by phenol disulphonic acid and nitrite by Griess Ilosva's reagent. Like benzylamine they were also not utilised.

In a similar way nitrobenzene and pyridine were studied and none of them were available to azotobacter. The above observations show that the aromatic compounds containing NO_2 , NO , or NH_2 groups are not utilised by the bacteria even if these groups are present in the side chain.

TABLE I

(Figures represent the percentage of the substrate utilised.)

o hr.	Semicarbazide.				Butylamine.		
	10 ⁻² .	10 ⁻³ .	10 ⁻⁴ .	10 ⁻⁵ .	10 ⁻⁶ .	10 ⁻² .	10 ⁻³ .
0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	14.3	0.0	0.0
6	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.6	28.6	0.0	0.0
8	0.0	0.0	10.6	23.1	50.0	0.0	0.0
10	0.0	8.0	21.1	34.7	57.2	0.0	10.0
12	6.7	12.0	36.9	46.2	64.3	0.0	20.0
14	13.4	24.0	42.2	57.7	85.8	0.0	30.0
16	20.0	36.0	52.7	69.3	100.0	0.0	45.0
18	24.0	40.0	...	...	...	0.0	...
20	34.3	...	...	100.0	...	5.3	60.0
22	40.0	...	...	...	...	15.8	70.0
24	...	...	94.8	...	...	...	...
26	...	...	100.0	...	...	34.2	90.0
28	...	...	84.0	...	...	42.2	...
29	...	...	...	...	...	...	100.0
30	70.7	88.0	...	...	...	57.9	...
32	73.4	96.0	...	...	...	68.5	...
34	80.0	100.0	...	...	...	84.2	...
36	85.7	...	...	...	...	89.4	...
38	90.7	...	...	...	...	100.0	...
40	100.0	...	...	...	...	...	...

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ON CUPRIC ETHYL ACETOACETATE

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The number of neutral chelate oxygen complexes with divalent copper is very large; the ethyl acetoacetate derivative forms crystals of peculiar green colour, insoluble in water and soluble in common organic solvents (Wislicenus, *Ber.*, 1898, **31**, 3153). Calvin and Wilson studied the stability of this chelate by the p_x titration method (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2003). During the present investigation the composition of this chelate has been studied by the thermometric titration method of Dutoit (*J. chim. phys.*, 1921, **19**, 324).